

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

First update of Collaboration plan

Deliverable D7.6

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.6

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

The present deliverable describes synergies and collaboration with the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) CASTIEL 2 (Grant No 101102047) and the EuroHPC JU Centers of Excellence (CoE) complementary to ESiWACE3. This deliverable is an update of the information recollected in Deliverable 7.5 - "Collaboration plan with definition of common objectives and activities, including milestones" (D7.5) that can be found [here](#).

The activities reported here include identifying common objectives, defining and implementing a collaboration plan, and defining related project-specific milestones. This collaboration plan will be updated whenever significant changes arise, at least in months 35 and 47.

2. Conclusion & Results

The "Collaboration Plan" is described in section 4. This section briefly describes the advances and results achieved within this first year of ESiWACE3, updating the information reported in the previous D7.5 and implementing the collaboration strategy with CASTIEL 2, the host entities, the National Competence Centers (NCCs), and other CoEs. This document will be changed and adapted as necessary as the project evolves, following the guidelines of CASTIEL 2. Updates to this plan are foreseen in the progress reports (months 35 and 47).

Several important results coming from the mutual interaction among the CoE and CASTIEL 2 can be highlighted at this stage of the project execution. The following lists the main results in which the ESiWACE3 Consortium has and is actively participating:

- Deliverable 2.4 - Legacy Software Report
- White Book of CoE HPC
- CI/CD pilot platform
- Collaboration Agreement
- Several events organised by CASTIEL 2 to which ESiWACE3 attended (HANAMI Kick off, CoEs meeting at EuroHPC Summit week 2024, CoEs industry "champions" meetings)
- Training material and content for popularisation and dissemination of ESiWACE3 and CoE's actions (ENES HPC 2024 workshop, HiPEAC 2024, ISC, SC)

3. Project Objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
A1: Transfer and establish knowledge and technology	Yes
A2: Close common technology gaps	N/A
A3: Serve as a sustainable community hub	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
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O4: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services	Yes
O5: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	Yes
O6: Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth System modelling across Earth System science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	Yes

4. Collaboration with CASTIEL 2

The collaboration with CASTIEL 2 is detailed in the corresponding deliverable of this CSA. The following subsections provide a summary. In order to strengthen and structure the interaction with CASTIEL 2, the ESiWACE3 Consortium designated several representatives to attend the different coordination activities and groups promoted by CASTIEL 2, like the Project Management Team (PMT)-CoE leader meetings, CAB, NCC/CoE networking, Legal tasks, CoE/NCC Industry support group, Communication, and Training.

5. Management

PMT meetings

The responsibility of the CASTIEL2 PMT working group is to ensure that the CASTIEL 2 project runs smoothly and in the correct direction. The PMT includes the CoE leaders to align work, share information and discuss next steps and general goals. Decisions of the PMT are binding and can only be overturned by the National Competence Centers and CoE Coordination Committee (C5) ¹. ESiWACE3 is contributing to the tasks of the PMT by participating regularly in the monthly PMT-CoE leader meeting organised by CASTIEL 2. During these meetings, ESiWACE3 representatives share feedback and recommendations in order to prevent possible risks from arising and look for corresponding mitigation measures to share with the other CoE representatives.

CAB meetings

The Competence Centre and CoE Advisory (CAB) is composed of the CASTIEL 2 Project Coordinator (or by the Project Manager (PM) or Deputy Project Manager (DPM) in their absence) as a chair, of 5 elected representatives of all the National Competence Centres and of the elected HPC3² officers. The National Competence Centres (NCCs) are the **central points of contact** for HPC and related technologies in their country, while the HPC3 is the HPC CoE Council, a key vehicle to ensure that the European HPC CoEs have an appropriate presence in the European HPC Ecosystem and in the actions of the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking. ESiWACE3 is contributing to the activity of the CAB and HPC3 by regularly attending the meetings and participating in a critical and constructive way to the debate about the role of the CoE and their way to interact and act within the HPC European environment.

¹ CASTIEL-2 Grant Agreement n. 101102047

² <https://www.hpccoe.eu/hpc-coe-council/>

Legal aspects and legal support - Participation in the Task 1.3 of CASTIEL 2

This task sets up an expert group of representatives of the NCCs and CoEs, covering diverse legal and political aspects. It will act as a forum for the NCCs to gather information on newly arising potential legal and political obstacles, for example, for the establishment of a sustainable legal framework for the NCCs during Phase 2 of the project³. For the NCCs and also the CoEs, it will provide legal support for securing further funding or for collaboration with various partners, e.g. SMEs or big industry. Furthermore, it will assist the NCCs and CoEs in addressing topics like the management of intellectual properties and licensing policies. The task will be led by legal experts or by representatives of each CoE with a technical background related to the different topics of interest. To this end, 9 working groups have been created.

ESiWACE3 is contributing to this activity by participating in one of the working groups (WG8) to fill the gap in the need for an explanation of IT law, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management of results, and software licensing-related thematics. The ESiWACE3 representatives from WP6 and WP7, even without direct legal expertise, will provide technical support through the experience developed in innovation and results exploitation and sustainability management inside BSC.

Collaboration Agreement

CASTIEL 2 set up a framework to act as a reference point for the NCCs and Centres of Excellence, promoting collaboration with each other and exchanging best practices and knowledge, all for strengthening the European HPC landscape and offering the best possible support to the user groups of these important technologies. The Collaboration Agreement proposed by CASTIEL 2 aims to set the rules of this collaboration by defining the rights and obligations of each Party involved in the CoEs and the CASTIEL 2 project. Thereby, it aims only to govern the relationship between the Parties not belonging to the same project. The relationship between the Parties belonging to the same project (the parties within each CoE activity or, respectively, the parties within the CASTIEL 2 project) are exclusively regulated in the relevant Grant Agreements and Consortium Agreements of these projects. ESiWACE3, with the support of the partners' legal representatives, contributed to the writing and acceptance of such an agreement by signature.

Communication

ESiWACE3 participates regularly in the meetings organized by the CASTIEL2 communication WP every month. ESiWACE3 uses the resources they have made available to us in order to be able to spread more of the activities/events organized within the CoE (like Slack channels and Workspace of NCCs and CoEs hosted by HLRS). ESiWACE3 We use HPC CoE social media to promote ESW3 content like the joint NCCs-CoEs Newsletter that CASTIEL 2 they are sending with all the activities

³ CASTIEL-2 Grant Agreement n. 101102047

6. NCC/CoE Networking and Mapping of Competences, Codes and Services

CASTIEL 2 Information Sharing System - C2ISS

CASTIEL2 starts with a set of websites (www.euroccaccess.eu, www.hpccoe.eu), which must be integrated into one unified platform solution. The new Web platform (working title: C2ISS) will not only include information about training offers but also about actors from the HPC system, their services & offerings and more. Figure 1 shows an overview of the individual components and services the C2ISS portal will support⁴.

Fig.1 Concepts of enhancing EuroCC Access connected with the C2ISS⁵.

ESiWACE3 and other CoEs will participate in periodic meetings coordinated by CASTIEL2 to ensure that ESiWACE3's needs are met with the new Web platform. At the moment of writing the CASTIEL2 updated the EUROCC ACCESS website⁶ with new content.

⁴CASTIEL-2: D5.2 Design strategy of the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC Access Portal

⁵CASTIEL-2 Grant Agreement n. 101102047

⁶<https://www.eurocc-access.eu/>

Collaboration between CoEs and NCCs

This mechanism is situated in CASTIEL 2 WP2, which is responsible for facilitating networking & collaboration across NCCs and CoEs and fostering NCC/CoE collaboration. The first step is to support the operation of a communication channel between all CoEs (the HPC CoE Council). ESiWACE3 was invited to join this mailing list channel, and we are following their communications. These communication channels will then facilitate regular discussions between NCCs and CoEs on topics of mutual interest to enable initiatives and working groups.

In parallel, CASTIEL 2 WP2 will define and run workshops on non-technical relevant topics and competences (soft skills, complementary competencies) based on the needs expressed by NCCs and CoEs—and make the materials available. Topics will either be sourced from the NCC/CoE discussions or from the knowledge CASTIEL 2 has from its management perspective.

Legacy Codes

Legacy Codes are software packages with a long lifetime of prior development. The majority of the big climate and weather models fall into this category. They tend to have large code bases written in Fortran and have evolved over decades. One of the objectives of CASTIEL 2 is to make available the majority of the HPC codes from the CoE on the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking (JU) systems, in a first attempt with proof of scalability on simplified dwarfs codes and then with the full production versions.

Many of these codes require software re-engineering to facilitate or, in many cases, even enable migration and maintenance on EuroHP JU systems (both current and future). One main task of ESiWACE3 provides software engineering services to help code developers from the weather and climate community in this effort, e.g. by porting codes to GPUs. ESiWACE3 is, therefore, well placed to help explain and identify re-engineering requirements for legacy codes in terms of personnel resources and time scales and to provide suggestions for actions to meet those requirements.

White Book of CoE HPC

CASTIEL 2 has put together a "white book" of CoE HPC codes to permit an easy overview of the use, adoption and deployment of the codes from the CoEs. This document gives a brief overview of all CoEs with their targeted application domains, their objectives, their HPC codes and workflows. Virtually all of these codes support CPU clusters, and many do support GPU clusters as well. Yet, individual scalability improvements are planned for many of them in the context of porting to EuroHPC JU systems. Some codes are already ported to one or several JU systems, while other ports are currently under active development. A summary of the current status, work in progress, and CoE plans for future porting to the JU systems is provided⁷. These plans will certainly evolve over the course of their respective lifetimes. ESiWACE 3 has contributed to exposing and exploiting synergies together with the other CoEs, providing detailed technical information connected to these efforts, most importantly, targeted scalability improvements, supported hardware, as well as parallel paradigms and APIs and 3rd party libraries employed. All the information collected is based on a selected subset of the input to Deliverable D2.4 by CASTIEL2.

⁷ see ESiWACE3 Milestone 25 and Castiel2 deliverable D2.4

Special access scheme

CASTIEL 2 will support the CoEs as ESiWACE3 in achieving appropriate resource access to the EuroHPC supercomputers to enable them to reach their objectives for deploying and delivering efficient, highly performant application software on the systems required for their users. For this purpose, CASTIEL 2 prepared several surveys to gather initial requirements for access to and use of the EuroHPC supercomputers (for development, benchmarking and performance optimisation) from all CoEs, including ESiWACE3. Based on a thorough analysis of the survey data, CASTIEL 2 compiled a detailed proposal submitted in project month 3 to the EuroHPC JU to justify a special access scheme specifically for the CoEs as a strategic part of the EuroHPC JU's programme.

7. Training

Training Framework

This task aims to facilitate access to training offered at the national and European levels to interested NCCs and other potential users (from industry, academia or the public sector). This includes improved coordination and increased availability of training activities on HPC across NCCs, CoEs, and within the European HPC ecosystem through the centralised training portal for training opportunities in Europe. This task will also establish effective cooperation and leverage synergies with other European initiatives in the area of training in HPC, including EUMaster4HPC⁸ and ETP4HPC⁹, among others. A common certification baseline of training and modular training approaches will also be addressed. This task will, therefore, establish a task force inviting, on the one hand, NCCs, CoEs as ESiWACE3, and the previously mentioned European initiatives, and on the other hand, certification experts such as the HPC Certification Forum and European certification agencies to jointly map out the situation and work on the training framework (which then is handed over to the CoEs and NCCs for prototypical implementation). Moreover, this task will coordinate defining and implementing the European HPC training baseline for industry, SMEs, academia/research/the public sector.

ESiWACE3 WP5 has a membership in the CASTIEL 2-coordinated task force for training materials. To that aim, ESiWACE3 is in direct contact with the CASTIEL 2 WP3 leader from BSC in order to strengthen the collaboration and interaction in the field of education and new training events. On the other side, at the moment of writing ESiWACE3 is assisting the development of NCCs/CoEs through several joint activities, like the NCC Italy and NCC Netherland virtual workshop in April 2024 and the NCC Austria workshop where ESiWACE3 representative will lead a tutorial on Kernel Turner in May 2024.

Mentoring & Inclusion

ESiWACE 3 is promoting, together with different CoE representatives, the organisation of a "Women in HPC" based workshop to promote the visibility, engagement, and inclusion of women and dissident genders in HPC to be held at the HiPEAC Conference 2025. There are different CoE representatives involved: ESiWACE3, PoP3, Cheese, MultiXscale, and MaX. To this end, an informal and volunteer-based

⁸ <https://eumaster4hpc.uni.lu/>

⁹ <https://www.etp4hpc.eu/>

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“Equity Diversity and Inclusion” (EDI) working group has been constituted with CoE female representatives and the Women in Science collective from BSC from all the departments. This is an volunteer group of different female representative coming from different CoE and from the EDI and Women in Science group in BSC that would like to promote the workshop at the HiPEAC conference 2025.

NCCs, CoEs – industry interaction support

ESiWACE3 is actively participating with two representatives at the activities organised by the CASTIEL 2 WP4, with one partner participating in the collaboration with HPC providers activity and with another in the collaborating with Industry meetings. These activities led to the presentation of the HPCW code internally and then to several presentations of the HPC service toward several NCCs.

8. Awareness, Impact

CI/CD Platform

The objective is to ease the deployment and support from CASTIEL2 to ESiWACE3 and the other CoEs applications onto some of the EuroHPC JU supercomputers. To lower this hurdle and enable ESiWACE3 code owners and end users to deploy applications with minimal overhead on multiple supercomputers, CASTIEL 2 coordinates the implementation of a common continuous integration and deployment platform across all EuroHPC supercomputers. ESiWACE3 actively participates in the monthly meetings, contributing necessary input, including information for CASTIEL 2 Deliverables 2.4 and 5.8. This involves sharing insights about our application codes and experiences in deploying selected applications on [LUMI](#). ESiWACE3 is committed to supporting the initiatives of this group and to providing the necessary assistance, aligning with the chosen applications and machines outlined in this document. This commitment is undertaken without compromising other planned activities within the Center of Excellence. Currently, ESiWACE3 is engaged in familiarising itself with the Gitlab Runner tool and updating our codes in the Gitlab repository. At the 1st periodic review and reporting period, ESiWACE3 agreed with EuroHPC and Castiel2 to focus the efforts in the porting and deployment of three main codes (NEMO, HPCW, Autosubmit) on the three pre-exascale machines in Europe: LUMI, LEONARDO, and Marenostrum5 (MN5). This deployment encompasses both CPU and GPU partitions, depending on the specific requirements of each application. Currently, BSC is in charge of collecting inputs from the steering group and the rest of the Consortium partners to understand the requirements and needs of the different partners and user communities, including other applications and deployments over different EuroHPC machines.

Supporting activities / CoE contribution to CASTIEL 2 objectives

ESiWACE3 has been active in the following activities/events together with other CoEs

- Workshop in collaboration with HiDALGO2 at HiPEAC2024 (January 2024)
- Contacts with ChEESE, MAX, HiDALGO2, BioExcel-2, etc., other CoEs through the HANAMI initiative
- Construction of the proposal for the implementation of the India-EU Intent of Cooperation Agreement in order to strengthen collaboration in HPC with India, addressing the priority domains of the HPC collaboration identified in the Agreement. (CoE involved: Bioexcel, ESiWACE3, Cheese)

9. Collaboration with Hosting Entities

Centres hosting the EuroHPC JU machines:

- **BSC, CSC, and JSC** which are also ESiWACE3 partners. These partners will, in particular, implement their HPCW Benchmark on those machines.
 - BSC, CSC and JSC will support the deployment of HPCW and climate and weather applications on MN5 and LUMI, providing guidance to ensure that the different applications are taking advantage of the CPU and GPU partitions efficiently.
- ESiWACE3 expects that the contact with **other hosting** sites will be facilitated by CASTIEL 2, and we aim at porting HPCW to several sites providing those sites show interest and will provide the necessary support.
- ESiWACE3 will also encourage the experts at other hosting sites (and other organisations involved in CASTIEL 2) to send their experts to support ESiWACE3 training events (and vice versa) to facilitate networking and knowledge transfer.
 - Collaborating to the 1st ESiWACE3 Hackathon, "[Running weather and climate models on LUMI](#)" (2023)
 - Collaboration to the 2nd ESiWACE3 Hackathon Jun 24, 2024 to Jun 26, 2024 "[ESiWACE3 Hackathon on Optimisation and Tuning of Earth-System Models](#)"
 - Collaboration to the ESiWACE3 - WarmWorld Summer School, Aug 27, 2024 to Sep 02, 2024 "[ESiWACE3-WarmWorld Summer School on HPC for Climate and Weather Applications](#)"
- Activities of deployment and porting HPCW-core + ICON and other dwarfs code on LUMI, MN5 and Leonardo started.

Interaction with Centers of Excellence (CoEs)

The ESiWACE3 project has selected the following CoEs whose activities are complementary and with whom potential synergies would be more effective. It is interesting to note that most of the CoEs should have some co-design activities (hardware, software, codes), including the collaboration with HPC vendors and the identification of suitable applications relevant to the development of European HPC technologies towards exascale and collaboration with European initiatives (e.g. EPI, RISC- V, EuroHPC JU Pilots). Thus, co-design is a common topic that can certainly lead to close collaborations with all CoEs. Table 1 shows the main CoEs of interest for ESiWACE3. **Table 1** shows the main CoE identified at the moment of writing for on-going collaboration with ESiWACE3.

Table 1. Centres of Excellence of main interest for ESiWACE3.

CoE acronym and title	Coordinator	Summary	ESiWACE3 partners involved
CHEESE 2P - Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Exascale in Solid Earth Phase 2	Geosciences Barcelona (GEO3BCN – CSIC)	ChEESE is the Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Exascale in Solid Earth. It aims to become a hub for HPC software within the solid earth community. ChEESE aims to address the challenges posed by geohazards and accurate predictions with	BSC, Atos

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CoE acronym and title	Coordinator	Summary	ESiWACE3 partners involved
		the help of exascale computers.	
eflows4HPC - Centre of Excellence (CoE) for workflows in HPC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)	eflows4HPC is a workflow platform integrating methodologies to widen access to HPC to selected user communities. It aims to design complex applications in integrating HPC processes, data analytics, and AI.	BSC, CSC, CMCC, Atos
BioExcel-3 - Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Computational Biomolecular Research	KTH Royal Institute of Technology (KTH)	BioExcel-3 provides open-source molecular modelling and simulation software, applications, tools, user support, and community-building events for Life Scientists. This will enable Life Scientists to address grand scientific challenges by fully exploiting the power of data and computing e-infrastructure.	BSC, CSC
MaX - Materials Design at the Exascale	Istituto Nanoscienze - Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)	MaX is the Centre of Excellence (CoE) for the MAterials design at the eXascale. This CoE aims to upscale the MaX codes and their performance to multiple heterogeneous exascale architectures, endow these codes with innovative capabilities enabled by such architectures and co-design the hardware and software in collaboration with the relevant European stakeholders.	Atos, BSC, Julich
HiDALGO2 - HPC and Big Data Technologies for Global Challenges	Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC)	HiDALGO2's mission is to provide effective and accurate simulations covering global challenges. The information will be provided quickly, considering changing weather and traffic conditions.	Atos
MultiXscale - application co-design and delivery for multiscale simulations	National Institute of Chemistry	IT develops multiscale simulation software to solve societal challenges associated with biomedicine, the transition to sustainable energy, and civil transport by supercomputers. The goal of MultiXscale is to develop software for computationally efficient multiscale simulations running on (pre)exascale HPC systems. The computer simulation codes and developed multiscale workflows will be openly accessible to researchers and engineers, user-friendly, easy-to-install, and with sustainable user support.	BSC, JSC

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CoE acronym and title	Coordinator	Summary	ESiWACE3 partners involved
POP3	BSC	It provides performance optimisation and productivity services for (your?) academic AND industrial code(s) in all domains! Review the computational performance of the weather and climate models	BSC, JSC

A number of concrete activities have already been identified or planned for potential collaboration for the next months. **Table 2** summarises these initial actions planned to collaborate effectively with complementary CoEs.. **Table 3** present a list of joint activities realized together with NCC and CASTIEL2. The list of actions and activities will be updated as the project progresses. We expect that the identification of further areas of cooperation between CoEs will be facilitated by the mediation of CASTIEL 2.

Table 2. Actions planned to collaborate effectively with complementary CoEs.

Collaboration activity	Title/Description	CoEs involved	Expected date	Venue (face-to-face/virtual)
CoEs management	Participation in the HPC CoE Council (HPC3)	ESiWACE3 + ALL CoE representatives	period	hybrid
Regular meetings to synchronise research and development activities	Eu - India digital partnership call (2024)	Cheese, Bioexcel. Within the framework of the Eu-India call, targeting a closer collaboration in the field of HPC between the EU and India, common activities between ESIWACE3 partners (in particular BSC, CMCC, Atos Bull SAS), BioEXcel, and Cheese also involving EuroHPC JU hosting sites, will be addressed.	September 2024	Workshops, conferences and exchange visits
Regular meetings to synchronise research and development activities	HANAMI	Within the framework of the HANAMI project, targeting a closer collaboration in the field of HPC between the EU and Japan, common activities between ESIWACE3 partners (in particular BSC, DKRZ, ECMWF), BioEXcel, and MaX also involving EuroHPC JU hosting sites, will be addressed.	Starting October 2023	Collaboration within a project
Best practices	Investigate the possibility of leveraging existing educational initiatives to introduce the concept of	ESiWACE3, MAX	Mid 2024	Virtual/Face-to-face. Depending on the format of

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Collaboration activity	Title/Description	CoEs involved	Expected date	Venue (face-to-face/virtual)
	CoEs and simulation to high school students. The objective is threefold: outreach, education, and promoting female profiles in computing. After this pilot, we would explore the possibility of creating additional educational materials (D6.1).			the existing initiatives.
Joint publication and dissemination of results	Not yet available	Potentially all. We expect that this will be addressed in the general assembly of CoEs organised by CASTIEL2 (under the lead of CASTIEL2 WP3). In addition, we will discuss dissemination and publication during the specific cooperation with individual CoEs (D6.1).	-	-
Joint events: workshops, hackathons, etc.	HiPEAC 2024 workshop - Towards reliable Digital Twin: advancing applications and tools capabilities for Global Challenges	EsiWACE3, Hidalgo2	January 2024	face to face
	HPC workflows for climate models workshop (D6.1)	eFlows4HPC and Climateurope2	17 October 2023	CSC premises
	ESiAWEC3 2 nd Summer school	ESiWACE3	Summer 2024	CSC premises
	CoEs Open Day event	Potentially all CoEs. It will be addressed to high school students to raise their interest in HPC research careers.	First semester of 2024	BSC premises
	CASTIEL2: CoEs and NCCs online meeting,	Meeting organised by CASTIEL2 to present the project and establish a first contact with the CoEs and the NCCs.	April 2024	Remote
Common best practices for IP management	Legal task implication	To be defined yet-	TBD	TBD
Concrete measures for identification of common routines/algorithms	CI/CD groups and legacy software activities (Gitrunner, deployment on pre-exscale machines)	ALL (CASTIEL 2 activity)	On going	Hybrid

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Collaboration activity	Title/Description	CoEs involved	Expected date	Venue (face-to-face/virtual)
/modules				
Creation and extension of software libraries used by multiple codes across disciplines	Technical tables database filled by all the technical representatives from CoEs	ALL CoE	On going	Hybrid

Table 3. Actions planned to collaborate with NCC and CASTIEL 2

Collaboration activity	Partner	Date	Venue (face-to-face/virtual)
Participation on a webinar organised on High Performance Computing (HPC) in weather & climate simulations	NCC Netherlands + NCC Italy	02/04/2024	Virtual
Organisation of an online training event on Energy efficiency with Kernel tuner	NCC Austria	12-13/09/2024	Virtual
Participation of CASTIEL2 (Ci/CD – Dennis Hoppe) at ESiWACE 3 General Assembly 2023	CASTIEL 2	November 2023	Virtual
Presentation of ESiWACE3 within the CoEs session organised by CASTIEL2 at the EuroHPC Summit 2023	CoE / CASTIEL2	March 2023	Face to face
Presentation of ESiWACE3 within the CoEs session organised by CASTIEL2 at the EuroHPC Summit 2024	CoE / CASTIEL2	March 2024	Face to face

5. References

- CASTIEL2 (GA 101102047) (2023) *Collaboration Plan with the CoEs - Deliverable 1.7.*
- CASTIEL2 (GA 101102047) (2023) D2.4 - Legacy Software Report
- ESiWACE3 D6.1. (2023). *Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan - Deliverable D6.1*
<https://zenodo.org/record/8098830>

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

This document is an update of the first collaboration plan that sets the basis for collaboration in the following years. It will be updated periodically.

7. How does this deliverable contribute to the EuroHPC strategy

This deliverable, by describing synergies and collaboration with the CASTIEL 2 and the other CoEs complementary to ESiWACE3, contributes to the EuroHPC JU strategy to develop the necessary technologies applications, and skills for reaching exascale capabilities and to develop and support a highly competitive and innovative high-performance computing ecosystem in Europe.

8. Sustainability

To our understanding, most of the actions addressed in this document and, in fact, the collaboration plan itself are inherent elements of the EuroHPC JU strategy to create a vivid and sustained European HPC community. Specific collaborations like bilateral exchanges with other CoEs will also contribute to the more general CDEP actions of ESiWACE3¹⁰, which we always see as part of a longer-term community strategy.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

We are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

- Making this document available on the [project website](#)
- Making this document available on the [ESiWACE Zenodo Community](#) (the Open Access repository for scientific results)

¹⁰ ESiWACE3 D6.1. (2023). *Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan - Deliverable D6.1*
<https://zenodo.org/record/8098830>

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Publication list can be found in the ESiWACE 3 Zenodo repository¹¹ and in the D6.2 - Report of activities and first update of the CDEP (M18).

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

N/A

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N/A

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/about>

